

Hierarchical Structured Superhydrophobic Surfaces on Graphite Composites

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Abstract

A scalable thermal imprinting method and subsequent hierarchical structuring with metal oxide nanostructures forms superhydrophilic or superhydrophobic surfaces on graphite composites. Anisotropically etched silicon wafers serve as basis to create various microstructures by a thermal imprinting process on thermally conductive polymer graphite composites. Even after 32 times of embossing, the mold can be reused and restored by pyrolysis, ensuring its longevity and cost-effective process. Nanostructuring caused by sputtered aluminium or electron beam evaporated copper on the embossed microstructures and further oxidized with a simple hot water treatment offers a wide range of different hierarchical structures. The combination of microstructures and nanostructures with a low surface energy coating of stearic or lauric acid results in a superhydrophobic surface, which is completely water-repellent with a contact angle greater than 160° and low contact angle hysteresis lower than 5° . This work provides a deeper understanding of the effects of the interaction of aluminum and copper metal oxide nanostructures and thermally imprinted microstructures on surface of graphite compounds. It has been demonstrated that superhydrophobic surfaces can be created with both fatty acids. Lauric acid is easier to use due to its simple handling and reaches a maximum contact angle after 30 minutes of exposure time with copper oxide nanostructures of over 170° .

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1. Introduction

Superhydrophobic surfaces are advanced materials characterized by their extreme water repellency, based on contact angles higher than 150° and a low contact angle hysteresis [1]. This unique property can be achieved through the combination of structured surfaces, with increased surface roughness, and a chemistry giving a low surface free energy [1, 2], which is inspired by natural models known as the lotus effect [3, 4]. Superhydrophobic surfaces have a wide range of applications and due to their high water-repellent effect, they remain dry and clean [5, 6]. They are used for self-cleaning textiles [7], anti-icing coatings [8, 9], oil-water separation technologies [10], water harvesting [11–13], heat transfer enhancement [14–16], and seawater desalination [17].

The surface structure has a significant influence on the wetting behavior. When investigating the wetting mechanisms, a distinction is made between two states: the heterogeneous Cassie-Baxter state and the homogeneous Wenzel state as depicted in Figure 1.1. The Cassie-Baxter state is characterized by the liquid being supported by air pockets within the surface roughness. Conversely, the Wenzel state involves the liquid fully penetrating the surface structure. The variation in surface wetting is also evident in the sliding behavior of water droplets which markedly improves heat transfer in falling films [18, 19]. In the Wenzel state, the adhesive forces between the water and the surface are significantly higher, resulting in considerably greater contact angle hysteresis compared to the Cassie-Baxter state [20]. A further improvement in superhydrophobization and sliding behavior [21] can be seen when the microstructured surface is covered with nanostructures and form so-called hierarchical structures, which is also due to a reduced wetted area [3]. There are a variety of methods that are used to create hierarchical structures, e.g. direct laser writing [22], soft-lithographic imprinting [23], electron-beam lithography [24], deep reactive ion etching [25], chemical etching [26], deposition [27], two-photon polymerization [28] and so on.

Figure 1.1.: Scheme of Cassie-Baxter (l) and Wenzel (r) wetting behavior.

However, when it comes to the superhydrophobization of thermoplastic polymers, the process of thermal imprinting has aroused the interest of researchers. Berendsen *et al.* [29] introduced an

injection molding process in which polystyrene (PS) and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) were embossed with a nickel stamp, which was produced by direct laser writing lithography and subsequent nickel plating resulting in contact angles of 167° and a contact angle hysteresis of less than 5° . Lin *et al.* [30] used commercial sand paper with different roughnesses to create arbitrarily structured polymer coatings with comparatively high contact angles but poor sliding behavior. A two-step approach for hierarchical structures on fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP), poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) and PMMA is presented by Durrett *et al.* [31] with nanoimprinting and plasma roughening to achieve superhydrophobic properties. Zhan *et al.* [32] introduced a one-step thermal embossing method to form hierarchical structures on polypropylene (PP) with a titanium mold produced by femtosecond laser processing. The modified PP is resistant to rough cleaning and mechanical abrasion, which retained a contact angle of over 150° and a contact angle hysteresis of $4-7^\circ$ even after over 100 cycles of sandpaper abrasion. When comparing these methods it is noticeable that the hierarchical structuring is always arbitrary and cannot be influenced precisely. A more precise alignment and arrangement of the structures would result in an enhanced hydrophobic behavior and longer a durability.

This work presents a scalable thermal imprinting technique with microstructured silicon (Si) wafers, which serve as a mold during the embossing process, and a subsequent, precise nanostructuring with various metal oxides creating hierarchically structured thermally conductive polymer composites. The scheme of the Si molds used for this scientific work are depicted in Figure 2.1. A wide variety of shapes of the microstructures are possible using the thermal imprinting process. The size of the structures can also be precisely controlled by the production of the Si molds, diverse imprints of the graphite composite can be seen in the Supporting Information. For industrial application, a mechanical production, e.g. a roll-to-roll imprinting process described by Yi *et al.* [33], of the microstructures would be suitable because it is much more efficient and economical. The hot embossing process used here and the silicon wafers produced were suitable on bench scale. The embossed microstructured samples were sputtered with aluminum or with electron beam evaporated copper and the nanostructures were created by a simple hot water treatment according to Saadi *et al.* [34]. Due to the wide variety of metal oxide nanostructures of different metals and their alloys, the microstructure-nanostructure relationship can be precisely adjusted. In this work, delicate aluminum nanostructures were compared to larger, needle-like copper nanostructures, which, based on their morphology alone, show significant differences, whether with or without microstructuring. The interplay of different forms of hot-stamped microstructures and the diverse morphology of the nanostructures opens up a multitude of possible combinations. This hierarchical structuring, combined with a coating of stearic or lauric acid, creates a superhydrophobic surface with a contact angle $> 160^\circ$ and a low contact angle hysteresis $< 5^\circ$. The hierarchically structured surface without low surface energy coating has perfect wetting characteristics and a contact angle that approaches 0° . This is a simple and fast approach to produce various hierarchically structured thermoplastic polymer composites with scalable microstructures and a wide range of possibilities to create diverse nanostructures when using different metals or alloys. A surface treatment in order to generate superhydrophilic or superhydrophobic surface properties expands potential applications.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials

Thermally conductive graphite-polymer composites, containing 80 wt.-% graphite particles and polypropylene as the matrix, were manufactured by the Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Center (Duisburg) with a thickness of 1.6 mm. More information about these polymer composites can be found in Kiepfer *et al.* [35].

Anisotropically etched silicon (Si) wafers were produced for thermal imprinting. The production of similarly prepared silicon wafers is given by Fotachov *et al.* [36]. The silicon wafers were used as molds in the embossing experiments. A schematic of the 3D topography of the etched Si wafers is shown in Figure 2.1. The wafer dimensions L are $30 \times 30 \text{ mm}^2$, the height H of the microstructures is approximately $20 \mu\text{m}$, and the width W of the etched structures ranges from $60 \mu\text{m}$ to $120 \mu\text{m}$ in $20 \mu\text{m}$ intervals.

Figure 2.1.: Scheme of the Si molds showing top view (l) and profiles (r).

2.2. Preparation of the superhydrophobic surface

To fabricate the superhydrophobic surfaces, four subsequent steps are carried out. Prior to this, the graphite polymer compound was cut into square samples of $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ and then cleaned in an ultrasonic bath in acetone, isopropanol and deionized (DI) water for 10 min each. The SI wafers have the same cleaning steps. All chemicals used in the experiments were analytical grade reagents and were used as received.

Thermal imprinting

A TA.XTplus texture analyzer (Stable Micro Systems, England) was used for the thermal imprinting of the microstructures. The device is typically designed for tensile and compression tests. An embossing die was developed to make the machine suitable for thermal imprinting. A conventional 50 W 12 V heating cartridge from a 3D printer was inserted into the embossing stamp so that the die can be tempered accordingly. The temperature is regulated via the current and voltage of a connected laboratory power supply unit. The temperature is measured inside the tip of the embossing die by a NiCr-Ni type K thermocouple (Ahlborn, Germany). The scheme of the thermal imprinting setup can be seen in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2.: Image (l) and scheme (r) of the set-up of the thermal imprinting experiments.

The silicon wafer is attached to the die with a double-sided adhesive thermal pad and the die is then screwed to the arm of the Texture Analyzer A.XTplus. The maximum current of 2.5 A is set on the laboratory power supply. Meanwhile, the graphite composite sample is placed on the sample table under the die. After a temperature of 230°C has been reached, the experiment is started. The die is driven towards the sample and exerts a force of 450 N, which corresponds to a

pressure of 0.5 MPa, on the sample over a period of 360 s. A temperature higher than the melting temperature of polypropylene is deliberately set because the sample is at room temperature before the compression and the test stand is not thermally insulated from the environment. The temperature drops to 115°C a few seconds after the start of the compression test. The pressure of 450 N and the high temperature at the stamp base ensure that the graphite composite reaches the glass temperature and that the wafer can penetrate into the sample at the beginning of the test before the temperature drops. This allows the negative of the silicon mold to displace the graphite composite and the desired microstructures are imprinted on the surface.

Metal coating

To form the metal oxide nanostructures (MONSTRs) on the surface, it is necessary to coat the graphite compounds with a layer of metal. The metal coating can be deposited using e.g. sputtering or electron beam evaporation. An aluminum layer was deposited on the samples with a sputtering system (Oerlikon UNIVEX 450 C, Leybold, Germany). The samples were sputtered with argon plasma at 300 W and a gas flow of 30 sccm for 15 min, resulting in an aluminum layer of 200 nm. Copper was also applied via sputtering at the same conditions. In order to be able to compare the surface quality of the coating method, the copper layer was also applied by electroplating and electron beam evaporation. For electron beam evaporation (Classic 500 L, Pfeiffer, Germany) the samples were coated at 300 W for 12:30 min resulting in a copper layer of 200 nm.

Nanostructuring

The MONSTRs were processed according to Saadi *et al.* [34]. The metal layer was oxidized within a simple hot water bath. A beaker with deionized water (DI) was placed in a thermostat (Alpha RA 8, Lauda, Germany). The aluminum coated samples were immersed in the hot water bath for 15 minutes at a temperature of 75°C and the copper coated samples were immersed in the hot water bath for 48 h at a temperature of 75°C. The temperature was measured with a NiCr-Ni type K thermocouple (Ahlborn, Germany). In addition, compressed air was injected at the bottom of the beaker throughout the oxidation, which ensured better mixing of the DI water in terms of the temperature gradient and a saturation with oxygen in the liquid. To reduce the long oxidation time of the copper surface, the surface can also be treated with a mixture of 2 M sodium hydroxide solution (NaOH) and 0.1 M potassium peroxodisulphate ($K_2S_2O_8$) for 10 min at room temperature as described by Bethke *et al.* [37]. The success of the copper nanostructures can be visually tracked, as the copper surface turns deep black due to the structuring, similar to black silicon. After oxidation the nanostructured samples are rinsed in a DI water bath to remove contaminants. They are dried at room temperature for 24 h.

Low surface energy coating

As a final step, a low surface energy coating was added in the MONSTRs processing. To investigate the influence of the chain length of the low surface energy coating two different fatty acids, lauric acid (Fisher Scientific, Germany) stearic acid (Omnilab, Germany), were used for this purpose. According to Lotz [38] a stearic acid coating was applied using a supersaturated solution of 2 wt.-% (48 mmol/L) stearic acid in heptane at 50°C for 10 min. Excess fatty acid was rinsed off with heptane after the coating at 50°C. Lauric acid was dissolved in ethanol ac-

according to Bethke *et al.* [37]. The influence of the influence of the lauric acid concentration and exposure time of the lauric acid bath was also investigated. Three lauric acids concentrations were prepared with 5 mmol/L, 10 mmol/L and 20 mmol/L. The static and dynamic contact angle was measured every 15 min for 1 h and after 24 h to see how the wetting behavior and the lauric acid coating changes over time.

2.3. Surface characterization

For cross-section measurements, 3D topographic and surface roughness, a laser confocal microscope (μ Surf Explorer, NanoFocus, Germany) was used. The evaluation of the confocal microscope images was carried out with the program MountainMaps. For a more detailed view of the micro- and nanostructures of the hierarchically structured polymer compound, scanning electron microscope (SEM, SU8000, Hitachi, Japan) images were taken with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. The static and dynamic contact angle measurements were performed with an optical contact angle goniometer (OCA 15EC, DataPhysics, Germany). The fluid used for the contact angle measurement was DI water and the volume of a drop was 8 μ l. For dynamic contact angle measurements the needle-in method was used. An 8 μ l DI water droplet was placed on the surface, and the needle was inserted into the droplet. The machine then pumped 40 μ l into the drop to measure the advancing contact angle and subsequently pumped 40 μ l out of the drop to measure the receding contact angle. The difference between the advancing and receding contact angles is the contact angle hysteresis. The values of the contact angle measurements were automatically obtained using the SCA20 software from DataPhysics. The high-speed camera (IDT OS8, Imaging Solutions, Germany) recordings were performed at 4000 fps, using a high-performance LED light source (IDT/ Veritas Constellation 120E, Imaging Solutions, Germany). The droplet that fell onto the surface was produced with a 500 μ L Hamilton syringe, which is also used for contact angle measurements.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Surface morphology of the imprinting experiments

The 3D surface profile of the Si wafer, depicted in Figure 3.1, and the top-view scanning electron microscope (SEM) images in Figure 3.2 provide a comprehensive view of the wafer surface characteristics. These figures reveal that the surface exhibits a smooth, angular microstructured morphology, characterized by well-defined edges and periodic patterns. The cross-section measurement of the example of the 60 μm Si mold in Figure 3.1 b) illustrates a height of approximately 19 μm of the etched structures and highlights the perpendicularity of the sharp edges. All confocal microscope images and cross-section measurements of the other Si molds can be found in the Supplementary Information.

Figure 3.1.: a) 3D profile of the silicon wafer captured by a confocal microscope and b) cross-section measurement showing the height of the 60 μm structured Si wafer.

Figure 3.2.: Top view SEM images of the Si wafers with a) 60 μm , b) 80 μm , c) 100 μm and d) 120 μm etched structures.

The 3D topography and a SEM image of the untreated compound are presented in Figure 3.4. These images reveal that the surface of the unembossed compound exhibits a high degree of roughness, indicating significant textural variations. The measured mean arithmetic roughness S_a of the compound is 2.0 μm , which is more than 20 times higher compared to stainless steel 1.4571 [35]. However, it must be taken into account that the manufacturing methods and the different forms of graphite particles, their particle size distribution and the different types of PP have a considerable influence on the surface properties of the composite and the mean arithmetic roughness S_a [35].

Figure 3.3.: a) 3D profile by a confocal microscope and b) top view SEM image of the untreated graphite compound.

Figure 3.4.: 3D profiles of imprinted compounds captured by a confocal microscope for a) 60 μm , c) 80 μm , e) 100 μm , g) 120 μm columns and top view SEM images for for b) 60 μm , d) 80 μm , f) 100 μm , h) 120 μm columns.

As the hot embossing machine lacks an adiabatic chamber and the samples were not preheated, the temperature decreased to approximately 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ due to heat conduction over the imprinting time of 360 s. After thermal imprinting, the Si wafer can be easily demolded after cooling without damaging the fragile mold, even though no additives such as lubricants or fatty acids were used for surface treatment of the imprinting matrices compared to the literature [32]. The results of the surface structures of the embossed compounds are shown in Figure 3.4. The surface of the imprinted composites replicates the negative structures of the Si wafer molds, resulting in periodic columnar structures with a height H of approx. 20 μm . The 3D profiles and cross-sectional measurements indicate that larger structures have more rectangular and sharper edges. However, it is demonstrated that 60 μm structures can also be successfully imprinted onto the polymer composites and easily be demolded without additives. As the structures become smaller, more defects and broken spots appear, caused by the significant interlocking of the microstructures during hot em-

bossing. Nevertheless, no missing columns were observed, and the height profile shows an almost rectangular shape up to 60 μm . Comparing the SEM and confocal microscope images of untreated sample shown in Figure 3.3 to the imprinted samples, the embossing process creates a smoother surface and seals imperfections such as microcracks or holes.

3.2. Wetting behavior of the microstructures

To characterize the wetting behavior of the surface, static and dynamic contact angle measurements were performed, as shown in Figure 3.5. To ensure good reproducibility of the imprinting process, each surface texture was embossed at least twice. The 3D profiles and cross-section measurements of all surfaces are provided in the Supplementary Information. The static contact angle increases from about 97° on the untreated sample to about 140° on the embossed samples, indicating improved hydrophobicity of the surface. However, the dynamic contact angle measurements show large contact angle hysteresis with significant error bars, indicating poor sliding behavior. The contact angle hysteresis of the untreated sample is the lowest, with an average hysteresis of 39° . All embossed compounds exhibit a larger contact angle hysteresis of more than 60° , which suggests a decrease in hydrophobic surface properties. The large error bars can be attributed to the pinning of the droplets to the surface. If the droplets remain in the Cassie-Baxter state during dynamic measurements, the contact angle hysteresis is low, at approximately $15\text{-}20^\circ$. If the droplets penetrate the structures and transition from the Cassie-Baxter state to the Wenzel state, they adhere strongly, resulting in large contact angle hysteresis of over 80° .

Figure 3.5.: Static and dynamic contact angle measurements of the thermally imprinted and the blank compound.

3.3. Hierarchical structuring and superhydrophobic wetting behavior

To obtain a completely superhydrophobic surface, nanostructures were applied to the existing microstructure, creating a hierarchical structure. A simple approach to generate nanostructures is demonstrated by Saadi *et al.* [34]. Various metals and alloys can be nanostructured through an oxidation step using a hot water bath. During oxidation, the metal oxides self-assemble into nanostructures, forming what are known as metal oxide nanostructures (MONSTRs). Since the wetting behavior of the embossed column structures showed no significant differences in the static and dynamic contact angle, the smallest embossments of 60 μm columns were used for the hierarchical structuring. The samples were coated with metal by sputtering aluminum or electron beam evaporated copper. Both coating processes resulted in a 200 nm thick metal layer. In order to investigate the impact of hierarchical structuring, embossed and unembossed composites were coated and later oxidized according to the method described by Saadi *et al.* [34]. Figure 3.6 illustrates the metal layers before and after oxidation. A comparison of the metal coatings reveals that the sputtered aluminum in Figure 3.6 a) has a rougher grain than the electron beam evaporated copper in Figure 3.6 b). The resulting MONSTRs of aluminum in Figure 3.6 c) and copper in Figure 3.6 d) are quite different and similar to literature findings [34]. It is also noticeable that the aluminum MONSTRs are finer and smaller than the copper MONSTRs and show a specific pattern of a just few nanometers, while the copper nanostructures form needle-like, non-directional columns of about 100-200 nm in diameter and a couple of micrometers in length. Furthermore, it can be added that there is no change in the morphology of the copper nanostructures whether they are oxidized for 48 h after Saadi *et al.* [34] in a hot water bath at 75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ or oxidized for 10 min with a mixture of 2 M NaOH and 0.1 M $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ at room temperature.

Figure 3.6.: Top view SEM images of a) sputtered aluminum b) aluminum oxide nanostructures c) electron beam evaporated copper and d) copper oxide nanostructures.

The hierarchical structuring and the high surface energy of the MONSTRs result in a super-

hydrophilic surface with perfect wetting behavior, where the contact angle approaches 0° and cannot be measured. This phenomenon is depicted in the the Supplementary Information. To achieve a superhydrophobic surface, a coating with low surface energy is required. Two different fatty acids, lauric acid and stearic acid, which differ only in the length of the carbon body, are investigated. Lauric acid has a C12 body and stearic acid has a C18 chain. According to Lotz [38], stearic acid is dissolved in a supersaturated solution with 2 wt.-% (48 mmol/L) heptane. The same practice was used for lauric acid to compare the results. The supersaturated solution of stearic acid is only homogeneous above 50°C and has a white fatty acid precipitate at room temperature. If you compare the two low surface energy substances with each other, it is seen that there is no difference in terms of the wetting and sliding behavior of the surfaces according to the coating with heptane at 50°C and a supersaturated solution for 10 min. However, it has a major influence whether the aluminum nanostructures are hierarchically structured or whether the aluminum MONSTRs are applied directly to the graphite composite without embossed microstructures. The hierarchical structuring with aluminum oxide has a contact angle of approximately $160^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ and a contact angle hysteresis of less than 10° . The pure nanostructuring of aluminum oxide compared to hierarchical structuring has a contact angle of 90° and a contact angle hysteresis of $38^\circ \pm 5^\circ$, which does not indicate any superhydrophobic surface behavior. In the case of copper MONSTRs, the hierarchical structuring has no apparent influence on the wetting behavior, since both forms exhibit superhydrophobic surface behavior with a contact angle of greater than $170^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ and contact angle hysteresis of less than $5^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. In most cases, no contact angle hysteresis could be measured using the needle-in method because the drop either rolled away when it was placed on the surface or when the needle was inserted into the drop. The static contact angle measurements are depicted in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7.: Static contact angle measurement of the hierarchically structured aluminum surface (l) and the copper nanostructures (r) both coated with stearic acid.

The C12 body of lauric acid dissolves better, e.g. also in ethanol and is homogeneous at room temperature. Due to these advantages and the easy handling three different solutions with 5 mmol/L, 10 mmol/L and 20 mmol/L lauric acid in ethanol were prepared to examine the impact of the concentration and the exposure time of the fatty acid for the copper oxide nanostructures. The fine aluminum nanostructures rapidly clog with the waxy fatty acids, which is why the experiments for exposure time and concentration of lauric acid were only carried out for the copper MONSTRs. Due to the long needle-like structures of 100-200 nm in diameter and a few μm in length, no differences were found whether the graphite composites were previously

embossed or not. This can be explained by the fact that the copper oxide nanostructures already form a hierarchical structure by nature and thus the wettable area is not reduced as compared to the aluminum nanostructures, which require embossing of the graphite composites to get superhydrophobic behavior. The impact of the lauric acid concentration and the exposure time can be seen in Figure 3.8. The highest concentration of 20 mmol/L has the highest contact angle after 15 min and reaches its maximum of approx. 179.8° after 30 min, after 30 min the contact angle decreases to 147° after 24 h. Similar behavior can be seen for the other concentrations. Their maximum lies always between 30 to 60 min and decreases after 24 h. The decrease in the contact angles after 24 hours can be explained by the fact that the lauric acid overgrows the copper nanostructures and only a few needle-like oxides still protrude from the wax layer. This can be confirmed by the top-view SEM recordings depicted in the Supporting Information as it shows a continuous layer of lauric acid with only a few copper MONSTRs.

Figure 3.8.: Impact on the static contact angle of the copper oxide nanostructures of the lauric acid concentration and exposure time.

To illustrate the superhydrophobic behavior a high-speed camera footage was captured at 4000 fps. In the footage, a water droplet of approximately 10 μl is seen falling onto the surface. Upon contact, the droplet is completely repelled and bounces off the surface without leaving any trace of wetting. This sequence of events highlights the surface's ability to repel water, and a series of selected frames from the footage is displayed in Figure. 3.9.

Figure 3.9.: Series of high-speed camera recording at 4000 fps.

3.4. Restoration of the embossing molds

After repeated use the Si wafer used for thermal imprinting may accumulate graphite composite particles on its surface. To clean the wafers and ensure they can be reused without contamination, the wafers are subjected to pyrolysis, heating them to 500°C for half an hour. This process burns off the contaminant particles. The effectiveness of the cleaning process is demonstrated in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.10.: SEM images of the 100 μm Si mold -as an example- after 32 embossings (l) and restored by pyrolysis (r).

4. Conclusion and Outlook

This study successfully demonstrates a scalable method for fabricating superhydrophilic and superhydrophobic surfaces on thermally conductive polymer-graphite composites using thermal imprinting and hierarchical structuring with metal oxide nanostructures (MONSTRs). The process involves the precise use of silicon wafers as molds, which can be repeatedly used and restored via pyrolysis, ensuring both longevity and cost-effectiveness. The combination of microstructured surfaces with additional nanostructuring and stearic acid or lauric acid coating achieved superhydrophobic properties, evidenced by a high static contact angle $>160^\circ$ for the aluminum oxide nanostructures and $>170^\circ$ for the copper oxide nanostructures and minimal contact angle hysteresis $<5^\circ$. The aluminum structures require a previous microstructured embossing of the surface, whereas the copper structures exhibit superhydrophobic behavior despite the need for thermal imprinting of the surface. The dependence of the contact angle in relation to the fatty acid concentration and the exposure time was demonstrated. All concentrations reached their maximum after 30 to 60 min with contact angles up to 180° . After an exposure time of 24 hours, the copper nanostructures were mostly covered by the fatty acid at all concentrations, which caused a decrease in the contact angle. The versatility of this technique opens up diverse applications in self-cleaning materials, anti-fouling coatings, and heat transfer systems, making it highly suitable for industrial implementation. The work highlights the potential of polymer composites in advanced material applications, particularly where surface properties are crucial.

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Nomenclature

Latin letters

H	Height	μm
L	Length	mm
S_a	Mean arithmetic roughness	μm
W	Width	μm

Greek letters

θ	Contact angle	$^\circ$
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Abbreviations

FEP	fluorinated ethylene propylene
PET	poly(ethylene terephthalate)
PMMA	poly(methyl methacrylate)
PP	polypropylene
PS	polystyrene

S. Supplementary Information

Confocal microscope measurements various thermal imprinted graphite composites

Figure S.1.: 3D profile of a 100 μm strip structured thermal imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.2.: 3D profile of a cylindrical structured thermal imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.3.: 3D profile of a half-rounded square columns structured thermal imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Confocal microscope measurements silicon molds

Figure S.4.: 3D profile of the 60 μm structured silicon wafer captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.5.: 3D profile of the 80 μm structured silicon wafer captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.6.: 3D profile of the 100 μm structured silicon wafer captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.9.: Cross-section measurement of the 80 µm structured silicon wafer captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.10.: Cross-section measurement of the 100 µm structured silicon wafer captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.11.: Cross-section measurement of the 120 µm structured silicon wafer captured by a confocal microscope.

Confocal microscope measurements thermally imprinted graphite compounds

Figure S.12.: 3D profile of the embossed 60 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.13.: 3D profile of the second embossed 60 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.14.: 3D profile of the embossed 80 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.15.: 3D profile of the second embossed 80 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.16.: 3D profile of the embossed 100 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.17.: 3D profile of the second embossed 100 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.18.: 3D profile of the embossed 120 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.19.: 3D profile of the second embossed 120 μm structured graphite compound captured by a confocal microscope.

Cross-section measurements thermally imprinted graphite compounds

Figure S.20.: Cross-section measurement of the 60 μm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.21.: Cross-section measurement of the second 60 μm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.22.: Cross-section measurement of the 80 μm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.23.: Cross-section measurement of the second 80 μm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.24.: Cross-section measurement of the 100 µm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.25.: Cross-section measurement of the second 100 µm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.26.: Cross-section measurement of the 120 µm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.27.: Cross-section measurement of the second 120 μm thermally imprinted graphite composite captured by a confocal microscope.

Figure S.28.: Contact angle measurement after oxidization without low surface energy coating.

Figure S.29.: Top view SEM recordings of the copper nanostructures coated with 5 mmol/L lauric acid after 24 h.

Figure S.30.: Top view SEM recordings of the copper nanostructures coated with 10 mmol/L lauric acid after 24 h.

Figure S.31.: Top view SEM recordings of the copper nanostructures coated with 20 mmol/L lauric acid after 24 h.